

AGRICULTURE HUMAN CAPITAL AS AN INVESTMENT IN BROADER AREAS

Senior teacher Khujamkulova Khosiyat Ishboyevna

doctoral student Salomova Zarina Murodovna

Annotation: The article highlights significant points about agriculture human capital as an investment in broader areas. In addition to this, recent researches and data about the theme were noted.

Key words: *human capital, critical thinking, multi-level impact, economic evaluation, agri-food systems, global agriculture development.*

Investment in agriculture human capital provide substantial long-term economic returns, such as enhanced productivity and reduced poverty. However, other crucial benefits can accrue from investing in human capital – resilience, creativity, innovation, confidence, quality of life, empowerment, gender awareness, critical thinking and stronger cohesion in societies. These benefits are related to more intangible factors such as wellbeing and livelihoods and cannot easily be monetised as income and productivity. These broader areas have relationships, though often nebulous, to economic benefits, and are also worth investing in, even if they prove difficult to show returns on investment . Empowerment, for instance, is a potential route to wellbeing. According to Friis-Hansen empowerment is an advanced type of participation whereby producers make the decisions themselves, rather than adhere to recommendations of others. Friis-Hansen and Duveskog state that empowerment may be more important than other technical solutions in agricultural development. A metaevaluation of farmer field schools (FFS) in East Africa showed a number of impacts ranging from food security and poverty to natural resource management, gender dynamics and wellbeing. Good health is generally considered to be an important component of

human capital.

Health could even be described as a reinforcing type of human capital, as it may aid learning abilities leading to new capabilities or knowledge. Nutrition thereby becomes interrelated with human capital as an input to good health. Nutritional diets, however, require the knowledge of and ability to produce, preserve and otherwise choose nutritious foods, which makes it a human capital of its own[1]. Therefore, investing in farmers' skill sets around nutrition can have a multi-level impact on different forms of human capital. Measuring economic returns on investment to an agriculture human capital project or programme may not fully capture all the outcomes and impacts, and the human capital contributions to general wellbeing, improved livelihoods and economic outcomes.

Since the early 1960s, economists have mainly written about the role of human capital's contribution to increased personal income and productivity growth, as well as national income and productivity. In the case of human and social capital, research has focused on strong returns on investment in the areas of studies, extension and education. Empirical evidence suggests that internal rates of return to public spending in agricultural research and extension are high. For example, the internal rate of return across Latin American studies averages at 53 percent, which is close to the average for developing countries . Indeed, returns to public spending in terms of agriculture productivity and poverty reduction have been shown to generally be the highest for agriculture research and development and education. Despite these research findings, however, little is known about how to effectively measure human capital in agriculture, or how to understand its economic value. Recent World Bank reports from the Human Capital Index provide some insight into measuring human capital with regard to education and health components[2]. As this study unfolded, we recognised the need to better understand the economic evaluation of agriculture human capital investment in investment projects. Thus, a technical working paper was developed

simultaneously to further contribute to the knowledge base on AHCI. The paper reviewed economic evaluations of human capital, described current practices and provided lessons for development programme designers and funding partners.

In order to understand the configuration of social capital among farmers, there must be a coherent model of how it forms. This paper adopts the multidimensional approach to the concept by Putnam and integrates various facets to define social capital in three different dimensions, namely structural, cognitive and relational social capital, as proposed by Nahapiet and Ghoshal and Uphoff and Wijayaratna. The main differences between the three dimensions are as follows. Structural forms of social capital, which refer to the interpersonal formation of linkages between individuals or groups, facilitate cooperation by lowering transaction costs and accumulating social learning. Alternatively, cognitive forms of social capital, including attributes such as a joint code or a shared paradigm that facilitates a common understanding of collective goals and proper ways of acting in a social system, even in the absence of specific links and relations between individual members of the group, predispose people to cooperate[3]. In contrast, the relational dimension of social capital, described as the type of (not necessarily longlasting) personal relations people have built up between them through a number of interactions result in cooperation being expected. For these reasons, we believe this approach to the concept of social capital is highly inclusive. Later in this section, we justify theoretically how the different attributes of each of these dimensions facilitate the combination and exchange of resources within the agricultural sector.

To sum up, all given facts it should be highlighted that Investing in farmers – what is known as ‘agriculture human capital’ – is crucial to addressing challenges facing our global agri-food systems, from sustainably feeding the world’s growing population with food that is safe, healthy and nutritious to finding innovative solutions for more resilient and climate-smart agriculture. Investing in

farmers is just as important as investing in infrastructure and other physical capital. Yet less than 3 percent of global agriculture development finance between 2015 and 2018 was invested specifically in strengthening the skills and capacities of agricultural producers[4]. Human capital, as an economic term, refers to assets that improve individual productivity. These include skills development, training and education, as well as public health and migration. They also include more abstract aspects such as self-esteem, empowerment, creativity, increased awareness and mindsets. In this report, the focus is on human capital in agriculture (including agriculture, fisheries and forestry activities) – that is, the skills and capabilities of small-scale agricultural producers to successfully manage farming enterprises. And it looks at individual human capital rather than that of organizations or groups, although these are important and linked to individual capital.

REFERENCES:

1. Aart, K. 2019. The World Bank Human Capital Index: A Guide. Oxford: Published by Oxford University Press on behalf of the WorldBank.<https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/34343>
2. Becker, S. 1964. Human capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, with Special Reference to Education. University of Illinois at UrbanaChampaign's Academy for Entrepreneurial Leadership Historical Research Reference in Entrepreneurship.
3. <https://madeagcessible.substack.com/p/two-kinds-of-investment-in-agricultural>
4. <https://reliefweb.int/report/world/investing-farmers-agriculture-human-capital-investment-strategies>

